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Developing the next generation technologies of renewable electricity and heating/cooling

MOSAIC

MOdular high concentration SolAr Configuration

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Executive Summary

Timely and effective dissemination of results is an essential part of every research project. This ensures that the gained knowledge or exploitable foreground can benefit the whole society, and that any duplication of research and development activities is avoided.

This document summarizes the strategy for disseminating the results of MOSAIC project and the activities planned to give high visibility to the project, its achievements and partners. Dissemination activities will be developed with the aim to support the project exploitation, trying to attract and involve the stakeholders through specific communication activities.

Dissemination and Communication strategy will be regularly updated so that all possible dissemination and communication routes are used during the whole course of the project. Also, any suggestions on dissemination from the project's External Advisory Board will be taken into special consideration. This document will be updated in M48 with the deliverable *D9.4 Final Communication and Dissemination Plan*.

EC rules for dissemination are summarized in Chapter 2: guidelines for internal communication, dissemination and publication of the project contents, with reference to the EC Open Access policy, are provided to partners. The quality assurance and approval process are also described. The target audience is defined as well as the corresponding communication strategy: project website, brochures, multimedia and social media are addressed to broad public; scientific publications, publications in technology news server and participation to conferences are addressed to the scientific community; workshops, events, press releases and newsletters are addressed to CSP community, industry, policy makers and media, etc. A Dissemination plan and corresponding timelines, able to create awareness is developed and presented in the Timeline subchapter.

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1. Introduction

Deliverable 9.2 *Draft Communication and Dissemination* is part of the task 9.4 *Dissemination and public events*. The task states that partners will define a working document outlining the dissemination strategy (definition of internal procedures, target audience, and timelines to publically disclose the results of the project) and communication strategy (means, methods and tools used to approach the defined target audience during the life of the project).

The Dissemination activities and plan will be updated periodically by the use of the **MOSAIC Intranet** and information about dissemination will be also included in the periodic reports.

The dissemination strategy has the objective to outline the main elements and strategic choices regarding the dissemination activities of the MOSAIC project towards the most important stakeholder groups. The document will enable the project team to properly plan and implement all required dissemination activities to achieve the identified main objectives: implement communication activities targeted to different stakeholders, produce publicity materials for project outputs awareness and involve the CSP community throughout all phases of the project. Actively participate in conferences, workshops, trade-shows and courses and foster relationships with other framework projects and initiatives (clustering activities) are key initiatives for the plan.

2. Dissemination and Communication strategy and plan

In relation to the external communication, it must be mentioned that the dissemination of the project's achievements should never jeopardize the potential protection of generated intellectual property (e.g. patent, product design) and further industrial application. Therefore, before any dissemination activity (publication, presentation) strict rules of prior notice to all partners will be applied, according to EC guidelines and stated in the Consortium Agreement. Partners will have the possibility to refuse dissemination of their own know-how (background or results) when it could potentially harm the partner's interests. The Dissemination Manager in cooperation with the Innovation and Market Coordinator will follow all the above described approval processes. They and the Project Coordinator will act as an internal executive approval body for any dissemination action organized by different partners.

All project outcomes will acknowledge the support of the European Commission as it is requested by the Article 29 (Dissemination of Results, Open Access, Visibility of EU Funding) and Article 38 (Promoting the Action, Visibility of EU Funding) of the H2020 MGA and follow its principles. Unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary must disseminate its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium). This does not change the obligation to protect results in Article 27, the confidentiality obligations in Article 36, the security obligations in Article 37 or the obligations to protect personal data in Article 39, all of which still apply. The proper dissemination details (e.g. time schedule for prior notice and partner's approval) is covered by signed Consortium Agreement (Article 8.5 Dissemination of results).

Prior notice of any planned publication should be given to other consortium members at least 30 calendar days before the publication. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement in writing to the Coordinator and to the consortium member proposing the dissemination within 15 calendar days after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit, the publication is permitted (Figure 1).

The following information will be always mentioned in the publication: **“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n°727402, project MOSAIC “**.

Figure 1: Information and timeline of intention of publication

The procedures to allow all dissemination materials to be quality assured including both the content and layout are established with the aim to check: (i) messages to be transmitted outside of the consortium, including the suitability of the messages for the people addressed, the stress on the benefits and the relevance for the industry (when applicable); (ii) technical contents control in order to ensure the quality of achieved scientific and research objectives of project brochures; (iii) that scientific papers and publications contain sufficient reference to the project; and (iv) layout quality and suitability to the standard.

2.1. Guidelines for partners

The European Commission is encouraging the Dissemination Leaders to record, track, monitor, coordinate and report all the project Dissemination activities (publications, participation to events, contributions to press and media) with dedicated deliverables and sessions inside the Periodic Reports. The **dissemination activities** session in **MOSAIC Intranet** has the aim to **track each partner's contribution, prepare a complete list of possible future actions and monitor/assess each dissemination activity.**

The following guidelines were provided to the partners as procedures for disseminating MOSAIC (i.e. submit a peer reviewed article, attend a conference, have a booth at a Trade Fair, publish press releases, post online information about the project, communicate with media, etc.):

- **Send an email to the Coordinator (TEK), Dissemination Manager (AMI) and to the other involved partners.** Please, remember the clauses of prior to notice, approval and acknowledgement in the CA.
- Once your article is published/ the conference or exhibition is closed/ the link of your contribution to media is available, please update the Dissemination session of the **MOSAIC Intranet Platform** with all the information required.
- **Each 6 Months there will be a review related to the dissemination activities,** including planning the next 6 month activities.

The benefits of having periodic recording of the project Dissemination activities is to provide regular updates to the EC about the project dissemination and coordinating the dissemination activities to maximize their impact.

Title	Activity Type	Main Leader	Start date	Finish date	Location	Audience type	Audience size	Addressed countries	Funding amount	Hyperlink	PSM Organisation	Languages
Article on the MOSAIC concept and project	Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularized publications)	IK4-TEKNIKER	06/02/2017 0000		Europe	Investors		Spain, Europe		Project Website	Magazine Empresa XXI	Spanish
Kick off meeting of a new Horizon 2020 project in IK4-TEKNIKER (EN)	Web site	RIOGLASS	17/01/2017 0000		Europe	Industry		Worldwide		Rioglass Website	N/A	Spanish, English
Meeting of a new Horizon 2020 project in IK4-TEKNIKER	Web site	IK4-TEKNIKER	18/01/2017 0000		Europe	Industry		Worldwide		Helioscop Website	Helioscop	Spanish, English
MOSAIC Kick-off Meeting	Web site	AMIRES	08/01/2017 0000		Europe	General Public		Worldwide		AMIRES Website	N/A	English
MOSAIC PROJECT WITH COBRA'S COLLABORATION	Social media	COBRA	04/01/2017 0000		Europe	General Public		Worldwide		Cobra LinkedIn Page	N/A	English
Press Release KOM MOSAIC	Press release	AMIRES	09/01/2017 0000		Europe	Medias	100	Europe			N/A	English
REUNION DE LANZAMIENTO DEL PROYECTO MOSAIC	Web site	IK4-TEKNIKER	13/01/2017 0000		Europe	General Public		Spain, Europe		Tekniker Website	N/A	Spanish

Figure 2: MOSAIC Intranet Dissemination Activities Recording

2.2. Publication policy and open access

Partners agree to generate peer-reviewed articles resulting from projects to an institutional or subject-based repository, for example Open AIRE, and to make their best efforts to ensure open access to these articles at the latest on publication or within six months after publication. **The open access to scientific publications will be ensured in line with Article 29.2 H2020 MGA on Open access to scientific publication and "green" or "gold" model would be used depending on the strategy of consortium with to the specific peer-reviewed scientific publication.**

Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer reviewed scientific publications relating to its results (Article 29.2 of what). In particular, it must:

- deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications; Moreover, the beneficiary must aim to deposit the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.
- ensure open access to the deposited publication at the latest:
 - on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or

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- within six months of publication in any other case.
- ensure open access to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication.

During the MOSAIC project's course various data will be collected and generated. It will mainly be the data acquired during the phase of the development and validation of individual technologies/components and data obtained during the tests in laboratories and on real testing sites. An appropriate privacy policy will be put in place and all necessary approval will be acquired before the deployment of the system. Anonymization of all data will be ensured. All data collected during the project will be placed in the MOSAIC Intranet, the project's repository tool, where they will be available for all authorized persons and will be properly secured against theft and misuse.

2.3. Timeline

The Figure 2 below displays the proposed dissemination and communication channels during the project life span:

Figure 3: Main proposed dissemination and communication channels

MOSAIC communication and dissemination activities are suggested as follows:

- development and maintenance of the project webpage
- preparation of the dissemination materials
- training activities
 - summer school / Reference course on STE technology (STAGE-STE project)
- organization of the MOSAIC events
 - workshops on the CSP theme
 - final MOSAIC conference
- publication of the MOSAIC results
 - at key conferences in Europe
 - in relevant scientific and industrial journals
 - contribution to technology news servers
- EU and national clustering activities

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- E-mail newsletters together with sister projects.

More in detail, **the MOSAIC dissemination plan foresees:**

- Phase 1 (M1 – M12):
 - press release summarizing the start of the project
 - webpage creation
 - implementation dissemination strategy
 - clustering activities
 - first MOSAIC presentations at events
 - preparation of the dissemination materials: factsheet, 1st Newsletter with sister projects
- Phase 2 (M13 – M24):
 - dissemination strategy update
 - continuous webpage update
 - clustering activities
 - scientific publications of the MOSAIC results
 - partners participating in conferences and symposia in CSP related domains
 - Summer/Winter schools CSP: Reference course on STE technology (STAGE-STE project)
 - dissemination materials: MOSAIC poster/roll-up and brochure, 2nd Newsletter with sister projects.
 - press release summarizing the first half of the project
- Phase 3 (M25 – M36):
 - dissemination strategy update
 - continuous webpage update
 - clustering activities
 - scientific publications of the MOSAIC results
 - dissemination materials: leaflet with projects' results
 - newsletter n°3 with sister projects.
- Phase 4 (M37 – M48):
 - continuous webpage update
 - dissemination strategy update
 - workshop
 - scientific publications of the MOSAIC results
 - final MOSAIC conference
 - final project video summarizing the whole project progress
 - newsletter n°4 with Sister projects / Press release summarizing the whole project results.

2.4. Target Audience

The goal of the dissemination and communication activities will be adapted to the different audiences. For instance, the consortium will apply all the mechanisms available to minimize the public resistance to the CSP solution, enhancing the advantages of this promising technology and showing that do not represent any risk to the society. In this sense, the WP8 and WP9 will be interconnected: WP8 will analyse the potential risk of the CSP technology and the mitigation measures and then, under the scope of the WP9, the members of the consortium will ensure that the outcomes are translated to the target audiences mentioned.

Various communication tools will be used and will be tailored to the needs of various stakeholders and audiences. The target audiences will include **scientific community, industry (Concentrated Solar Power, industrial cooling), policy makers, standardization bodies, students, public and the media**. The identified channels and tools for the communication (and dissemination) are introduced in the Chapter 4.

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Communication activities will be monitored and followed-up to maximize their impact. Project Officer will be regularly informed about the communication outcomes and based on her/his decision EC communication channels could be used too.

The following table shows the different audiences identified by the consortium and the instruments that will be adopted to reach them.

Table 1. Matrix of intended MOSAIC dissemination and communication channels and the targeted audience

MOSAIC dissemination routes	Broad public	Students	Research	Industry	Policy makers	Media
Project webpage	X	X		X	X	X
Project folders, leaflets	X	X		X	X	X
Scientific journals		X	X			
Technology News servers	X	X	X	X	X	
Presentation/conferences		X	X	X	X	
Final workshop		X	X	X	X	X
E-mail newsletter		X	X	X	X	
Social media tools	X	X		X		X
Press conference, press release		X				X

A role of a Dissemination Leader (WP9 Leader, Fabrizio Perrotta, AMI) has been established to plan, follow, undertake and monitor the planned communication and dissemination activities. Regular contact with all Work Package Leaders will ensure timely communication and dissemination of project outcomes and results.

3. Preparation of dissemination materials

Several types of dissemination materials will be prepared during the project's lifespan to create awareness and inform wide and various audiences on the MOSAIC project and its development. These materials will be extensively used by MOSAIC partners whenever they present at conferences, publish in journals and magazines, establish contacts with media, attend exhibitions, organize workshops, etc.

The promotional materials developed and under development during MOSAIC project are:

- Project logo
- Project webpage
- Project fact sheet and leaflets
- Roll-up
- Newsletters & press releases
- Social media

All the materials will be distributed to all the partners by email and uploaded to MOSAIC Intranet.

3.1. Project logo

The official MOSAIC logo (Figure 3) is also associated with the EU flag and acknowledgment. The project logo is used in all the project related advertising materials including templates, website, leaflets, posters, brochures and newsletters.

Figure 4: MOSAIC Official Logo

3.2. Webpage

MOSAIC website <http://mosaic-h2020.eu/> has been set up in order to increase public awareness of MOSAIC project. Final version of the webpage with information on the project has been reviewed by partners, and has been operational since 13th March 2017.

The MOSAIC website will be actively maintained during the whole course of the project. The whole content of the webpage is public. The website has been created in Open Source software called WordPress. WordPress started as a blogging system, but has evolved to be used as full content management system, that is completely customizable and can be used for almost anything within the field of web design. It allows fast and reliable customization and user-friendly back-office environment which is a key for the website updates and file uploads.

The content of individual pages is divided in 6 parts (frames): heading with project's logo, navigation menu with titles of the pages and subpages (visible as soon as moving the mouse on the page title), four moving photos of the testing sites provided by partners COBRA and CMI, a central area with content description related to the page, a moving bar with all partners' logos, a fixed bar with contacts, an calendar with projects events and news, useful project related links (Horizon 2020, INEA, CORDIS), and finally a footnote with the acknowledgment of EU funding and EU flag. The website contains also a search tool.

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The main navigation menu is placed at the top of the central area and includes the following sections (with their respective subsections): Home, Project with subsections Projects facts, Consortium, Work Summary, Technologies with the explanation of the MOSAIC concept, Dissemination with subsections Public deliverables, Scientific publications, Project Clustering and CSP training, News with subpages Projects, News, Events, Press release & Media and Gallery, Downloads and Contact us.

At the footnote of the website an acknowledgment of EU funding is placed: **“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n°727402, project MOSAIC “.**

Figure 5: MOSAIC Website Homepage

3.3. Factsheet and Leaflet

In order to provide broad public, with information about the project, a general information fact sheet will be prepared to provide a short, simple and easy to read overview of the project. It will be included general project information, an introduction about concentrating solar power as promising and sustainable renewable energy, basic facts and expected impact. Name and countries of partners, contacts of the coordinator, and the webpage link are also provided. The factsheet can be distributed both electronically and in printed form by each partner during events and meetings with stakeholders.

During the second year of the project, a leaflet with additional infographics about the project will be designed and distributed by the partners in the upcoming events. Information leaflets will be also prepared on M36 for presenting to stakeholders the results of the project. Additional materials can be created on partners’ demand.

3.4. Roll up

In order to make the presentation of the MOSAIC project in different events a roll-up will be developed including the general project information, the description of the MOSAIC concept and approach with visual contents, the logos of partners and the webpage link. Other posters with more scientific contents could be developed by the partners and presented during scientific symposia and conferences, showing with tangible results and data the achievements of the project to the CSP community and industry.

3.5. Newsletter and press release

The project newsletters and their regular dissemination can help to maintain the visibility of the project during its whole duration, create awareness and expectations regarding the final results and inform the target audience about advances made in the project. MOSAIC project has established a strong cooperation with sister projects and a conjoint newsletter has been planned together with the other H2020 CSP projects (See Chapter 6: EU clustering activities and events). CSP H2020 projects newsletter will be distributed at one year interval and aim to raise awareness about CSP and increase projects visibility and disseminate also the outputs of the projects.

The aim of the press releases is to attract media attention and increase public awareness of the MOSAIC project and its outcomes and events. This first press release of the project has been published after the Kick-off meeting in Eibar (Spain) with the goal to announce the starting of the MOSAIC project (Figure 6: KOM Press Release).

The second press release is planned on the M24 after the second year of the project with the goal to present the first outputs. The third press release is expected on the M46 when first results from the testing sites will be available. This press should promote the final MOSAIC conference and point out the most interesting results reached during the project lifetime. Press releases might be also published by individual partners to present their involvement in the project. Timeline of newsletters and press releases can be changed on partners' request.

Publications in magazines, press campaigns and media events by partners will be supported during the lifespan of the project under the approval of Dissemination manager, Innovation and Market Coordinator and Project Coordinator. Media will be invited also during the next key project events, especially during the last year of the project. All press releases, articles and multimedia news connected with MOSAIC project can be found in the section Press releases within the MOSAIC website and it will be recorded in the MOSAIC Intranet.

3.6. Social Media

Social Media like LinkedIn, YouTube, Twitter, etc. will be considered to address the potential impact especially to the younger generation and to have the feedback from various audiences. Short news on MOSAIC project and its development would be prepared and shared on the identified tools especially during events, conferences and symposiums.

Social media will be also considered as a communication channels to develop potential clustering activities. It is ongoing a discussion to create a conjoint LinkedIn group together with MOSAIC Sister projects.

MOSAIC KOM Press Release

BILBAO, 1-2 December 2016 — Kick-off meeting of a new Horizon 2020 project took place in Eibar (SPAIN), on 1–2 December, 2016. [MOSAIC project](#) aims to design, manufacture and validate an innovative CSP concept that will have low implementation costs at the highest plant efficiencies, compared to the current state-of-the-art technologies, and that will reduce the levelized cost of electricity (LCOE).

In particular, MOSAIC module consists of an innovative fixed spherical mirror concentrator arranged in a semi-Fresnel manner and an actuated receiver based on a low cost closed loop cable tracking system. This configuration reduces the moving parts of the whole system decreasing solar field cost while keeping high concentration ratios. This will assure high working temperatures thus high cycle efficiencies and a cost effective use of thermal storage systems.

The MOSAIC Consortium represents a multi-disciplinary group composed of 9 partners and 6 countries within the European Union forming an ideal and well-balanced team. MOSAIC partners are [IK4-TEKNIKER](#), (Spain - Coordinator), [AMIRES Sro](#) (Czech Republic), [Cockerill Maintenance & Ingénierie](#) (Belgium), [COBRA INSTALACIONES Y SERVICIOS S.A](#) (Spain), [CENTRO NACIONAL DE ENERGÍAS RENOVABLES](#) (CENER, Spain), [POLITECNICO DI TORINO](#) (Italy), [RIOGLASS SOLAR SA](#) (Spain), [Senior Flexonics GmbH](#) (Germany), [Sirea](#) (France). During the KOM, partners discussed technical issues related to the concept to be developed as well as potential dissemination and exploitation routes.

MOSAIC project has a duration of 48 months, please, stay updated about the upcoming project results!

Project website: <http://www.mosaic-h2020.eu/> (full version available March 2017)

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5,077,733.75 €

Figure 6: KOM Press Release

4. Organisation of MOSAIC events

Events organized by the MOSAIC project are suggested in two directives: organization of project workshop and final MOSAIC conference, and training activities such as winter/summer school. Consortium will explore and choose during the project the best options in order to organize high impact events. It will be highly encouraged the potential organisations of conjoint events with sister projects.

4.1. Project workshop and final conference

The consortium will organize several workshops in Europe on the concentrated solar power theme in order to promote the developed MOSAIC concept. One of these workshops will be organised in Brussels to attract the attention of policy makers, members of the European Parliament, representatives of regions, lobbyist organisations and other relevant stakeholders. Conjoint workshop organisation with other sister projects will be highly encouraged.

Final MOSAIC conference will take place in the test site to show the outcomes of the project in real time conditions. Detailed information about the conference including the exact content, speakers, targeted audience etc. will be discussed during the M36 MOSAIC meeting.

Testing site visit will be prepared for journalists to give them the latest information on solutions developed in the MOSAIC project and allowing them to inform the general public on the possibilities of CSP plants improvements.

4.2. Training activities

Besides the R&D progress, the important aspects for the consortium are training activities. The target group for the training will be especially CSP professionals and technicians. They will be identified by all consortium members based on their experience and collaborations. Well educated professionals in this domain are a prerequisite for a successful and effective usage of CSP power plants.

A specific seminar on the applications of CST technologies developed in MOSAIC will be organised in the last year of the project. The decision of the organization of this workshop will be adopted during the project execution taking into account the intellectual property rights and the willingness of the owners and partners involved in MOSAIC module. MOSAIC concept will be proposed as an additional technology to be included in the “reference course on STE technologies” developed during the STAGE-STE project and it will be potential presented in a conjoint seminar with sister projects.

Detailed information on the training activities will be inserted in the D9.5 **Reference material for reference course and winter/summer schools for CSP professionals** (M24, M48).

5. Publication of MOSAIC results

Publication of MOSAIC results to relevant scientific periodicals, journals, events and key conferences will be assured during the whole project lifetime. Publications will be periodically recorded in the MOSAIC Intranet.

5.1. Presentations at conferences, symposia, meetings

A set of conferences, workshops, and seminars in the CSP domain have been identified by partners to disseminate MOSAIC results. During these events the representatives of the project will have the possibility to communicate the project’s scope and possible interaction and exchange with initiatives and projects in the CSP field community.

Here are examples of events, where presentation of MOSAIC project will be considered (the list is not exhaustive and it will be updated):

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Conference	Partner	Description	Frequency
<i>SolarPaces 2018</i>	CMI- COBRA – CENER- POLITO- SIREA	By the year 2018 it has been foreseen that the system prototype will be designed and integrated. SolarPaces conference the system will be exposed.	2018, Annual
<i>CSP America</i>	COBRA	CSP technology in the American continent	Annual
<i>CSP Mena</i>	COBRA	CSP technology in the Mena region	Annual
<i>CSP Today</i>	CMI- CENER	Concentrated Solar Thermal Power Conference and Exhibition	Annual
<i>ISES</i>	CENER	Solar World Congress	Biannual
<i>ESTELA</i>	CENER	ESTELA's Solar Thermal Electricity Industry Forum	Annual
<i>ESTELA</i>	CENER	ESTELA's Summer Workshop	Annual
<i>ASME Energy Sustainability Conference</i>	POLITO	Focused on innovative technologies, research and design advances, solutions toward renewable and other energy sustainability options, utility-level integration.	Annual

Figure 6: Conferences where MOSAIC can be presented

Event	Partners	Website
<i>GENERA</i>	CENER	www.ifema.es/genera_01/
<i>Hannover Messe (tbc)</i>	SIREA	http://www.hannovermesse.de
<i>Salon Siane</i>	SIREA	http://www.salonsiane.com

Figure 7: Fairs where MOSAIC can be presented

Clustering activities with other projects will provide more opportunities to participate in dissemination activities.

5.2. Scientific articles in relevant journals and periodicals

Publication of MOSAIC results in relevant scientific and industrial periodicals and journals in Europe will be encouraged during the course of the project.

MOSAIC partners have identified potential topics to publish in the scientific and industrial periodicals and journals in Europe (Figure 8: MOSAIC Expected Articles).

Expected articles	Partner	WP
Competitiveness of technology	COBRA	WP9
Article on MOSAIC global system concept	CENER	WP2
Article on conceptual design of MOSAIC module	CENER	WP2
Article on MOSAIC solar receiver preliminary design	CENER	WP5
Numerical thermo-mechanical and thermo-fluid design of an optimized receiver for an innovative solar bowl system.	POLITO	WP5

Figure 8: MOSAIC Expected Articles

Examples of journals, where contributions from MOSAIC partners might be expected (the list is not exhaustive):

- Elsevier (<http://www.journals.elsevier.com/solar-energy/>)
- Energy & Environmental Science
- Journal of Energy and Power Engineering
- Science Bulletin
- Resource-Efficient Technologies

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5.3. Press and Media

During MOSAIC meetings, especially in the last year, local media will be invited to speak with coordinator and partners. Partners will use their websites to disseminate MOSAIC activities. IK4-TEKNIKER, AMIRES, RIOGLASS has already published on his website the first news after KOM and COBRA in his official LinkedIn page.

Partners are encouraged to proactively engaged dissemination activities with press and media by always taking into consideration the internal communication rules and EC regulation. Peer-reviews and non-peer reviews publications will be recorded on MOSAIC Intranet and display on the project website.

5.4. Technology news servers and others

MOSAIC project will comply with knowledge sharing arrangement and will actively contribute to technology news servers (e.g. CORDIS) and other initiatives periodically, each time after the latest achievements, at the latest at the beginning and at the end of the project.

6. EU Clustering activities and events

Clustering activities are essential and strategic for MOSAIC dissemination and it will be highly promoted by the consortium. The objectives are to address innovation and exploitation issues in running projects and explore potential for cross-project clustering.

On 24th November 2016, the Innovation and Networks Executive Agency (INEA) hosted a H2020 Coordinators' Workshop on Concentrated Solar Power. The aim of the workshop was to investigate potential synergies between projects in the area of Concentrated Solar Power. **Project Coordinator** (Cristobal Villasante) and **Dissemination Leader** (Fabrizio Perrotta) presented the MOSAIC concept and the potential dissemination and communication strategy. Furthermore, they participated in the group discussions to identify potential synergies and overlaps. The main follow up actions after the workshop are:

- Background and methodology benchmark between Sister projects
- Conjoint training, summer schools and workshops
- Common booth in key CSP conferences and events
- Increasing the stakeholders' identification and involvement

Following this workshop, four CSP Dissemination leaders from six ongoing CSP projects organised a teleconference on the 9th February 2017. The aim of this teleconference was to discuss and plan conjoint dissemination activities. Dissemination leaders agreed to share the information about the project websites, the events planned for each project, as well as it has been decided to have a conjoint newsletter and LinkedIn group. It has been also agreed to have by-monthly teleconference.

Similar activities are expected also at national levels. As disclosed in the next subchapter, partners have been working together in other projects so it is expected a high participation in clustering events.

6.1. Sister projects

Cooperation and synergies with other projects in the field of CSP by the European Commission will be used to enforce a rapid exploitation and potential cross-linking of project goals and marketing initiatives. Within this collaboration organization of joint events is expected as well as sharing important knowledge gained during the project.

To this aim, ongoing projects has been identified by the Consortium and the European Commission. It is planned that representatives of identified projects will be also invited to workshops and events organised by MOSAIC.

Following projects were identified as possible for clustering:

- **WASCOP** (Water Saving for Concentrated Solar Power): WASCOP aims to develop a revolutionary innovation in water management of Concentrating Solar Power plants, a more flexible integrated solution comprising different innovative technologies and optimized strategies for the cooling of the power-block and the cleaning of the solar field optical surface. **AMIRES**, **IK4-TEKNIKER** and **RIOGLASS** are partners in the WASCOP project. <http://wascop.eu>
- **MinWaterCSP**: The MinWaterCSP project aims to reduce water evaporation losses by 75 to 95% compared to wet cooling systems. It aims to increase the net efficiency of the steam Rankine cycle by 2%, or alternatively reduce the capital cost of a dry-cooling system by 25%, while maintaining cycle efficiency. <http://www.minwatercsp.com>
- **CAPTure**: The main goal of the CAPTure project is to significantly reduce costs of concentrated solar power (CSP), in order to pave the way for its deserved competitiveness on the power market. In order to increase plant efficiencies and reduce levelized cost of electricity (LCOE), the project will develop all relevant

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components that allow implementing an innovative plant configuration. CENER and IK4-TEKNIKER are partners in the CAPTure project

<http://capture-solar-energy.eu>

- **PreFlexMS:** The core objective of PREFLEXMS is to enhance the predictability and flexibility of Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) generation to address the evolving needs of regulators, grid operators and plant operators.
<http://preflexms.eu>
- **ORC-PLUS:** The ORC-PLUS project aims at developing an optimized combination of innovative Thermal Energy Storage (optimised for the CSP scale 1-5 MWe) and engineering solutions necessary to improve the dispatchability (production on demand) and number of hours of production of an existing small CSP plant, located in a desert areas and coupled with an ORC system.
<http://www.orc-plus.eu>
- **FP7 STAGE-STE** (Scientific and Technological Alliance for Guaranteeing the European Excellence in Concentrating Solar Thermal): it engages all major European research institutes in order to convert the consortium into a reference institution for concentrating solar energy research in Europe, enhance the cooperation between EU research institutions participating in the IRP to create EU added value, synchronize the different national research programs to avoid duplication and to achieve better and faster results, accelerate the transfer of knowledge to industry in order to maintain and strengthen the existing European industrial leadership in STE, expand joint activities among research centres by offering researchers and industry a comprehensive portfolio of research capabilities, bringing added value to innovation and industry-driven technology, establish the European reference association for promoting and coordinating international cooperation in concentrating solar energy research. **CENER, IK4-TEKNIKER and COBRA** are partners of the Consortium.
<http://stage-ste.eu>

MOSAIC (in particular the task T3.6) will benefit from the developments of the WP3 in WASCOP (Cleaning methods - WPL IK4-TEKNIKER) and MOSAIC concept will be proposed as an additional technology to be included in the “reference course on STE technologies” developed during the STAGE-STE project (T4.3).

7. External Advisory Board cooperation

The MOSAIC External Advisory Board has been created not only to support the consortium during the technical specification phase at the beginning of the project, validation of results and flawless results exploitation but also to increase the Pan-European concept of this project and provide desirable feedback from other closely related European or national activities.

The current list of EAB members includes the following representatives:

- **Mr. Luis Crespo** from ESTELA – European Solar Thermal Electricity Association.
- **Mr. Holger Gassner** from RWE Innogy GmbH.
- **Mrs. Sònia Clarena Barón** from EUTurbines - European Association of Gas and Steam Turbine Manufacturers).

The communication with EAB members is ensured through regular meetings (in person or through teleconferences) and through distribution of the CSP projects newsletter which is meant to bring the latest news on the MOSAIC project to the identified stakeholders.

8. Conclusions

This document represents the public Deliverable “*D9.2 Draft Communication and Dissemination*” of the project MOSAIC and it summarizes the strategy for disseminating the results of MOSAIC project and the activities planned to give high visibility to the project, its achievements and partners. The dissemination of the project’s achievements should never jeopardize the potential protection of generated intellectual property and further industrial application. Therefore, before any dissemination activity (publication, presentation) strict rules of prior notice to all partners will be applied, according to EC guidelines: prior notice of any planned publication should be given to other consortium members at least 30 calendar days before the publication. The Dissemination Manager in cooperation with the Innovation and Market Coordinator will follow all the above described approval processes. They and the Project Coordinator will act as an internal executive approval body for any dissemination action organized by different partners.

MOSAIC Intranet is the official Consortium tool to record each partner’s contribution to dissemination, and guidelines for dissemination and publication of the project contents, with reference to the EC Open Access policy, are provided to partners. List of main journals have been identified by partners. It is the role of the main author to propose fair and equal distribution of co-authorships and determine the order. Each partner is free to choose any national or international event or conference, which may be interesting for showing results from the MOSAIC project.

The target audience, including the advices received from the External Advisory Board members, is defined in the document as well as the corresponding dissemination routes: project website, leaflets, multimedia and social media are addressed to broad public; scientific publications, publications in technology news server and participation to conferences are addressed to the scientific community; workshops, events, press releases and newsletters are addressed to CSP Community, industry, policy makers and media, etc.

MOSAIC promotional materials will create awareness and inform the wide and various target audiences about the MOSAIC project and its development. These materials will be extensively used by MOSAIC partners whenever they present at conferences, publish in journals and magazines, establish contacts with media, attend exhibitions, organize workshops, etc.

Cooperation and synergies with other projects in the field of CSP will be used to enforce a rapid exploitation and potential cross-linking of project goals and marketing initiatives. Clustering activities are essential and strategic for MOSAIC dissemination and it will be highly promoted by the consortium.

This document will be updated in M48 with the deliverable *D9.4 Final Communication and Dissemination Plan*. This final deliverable will also include detailed information on the MOSAIC workshops, final conference, tutorials or summer school. Possible new routes will be further monitored and if found relevant they would be integrated in the communication, dissemination and exploitation road map.

When disseminating the results of the project, it will be always ensured, that following sentence is mentioned: **“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n°727402, project MOSAIC “.**

9. Degree of Progress

The deliverable is to 100% fulfilled. Task 9.4 “Dissemination and public events” will continue till the end of the project and the dissemination and communication activities and plan will be updated periodically (each 6 months) by the use of MOSAIC Intranet.

10. Dissemination Level

The Deliverable D9.2 is public and therefore it will be available to download on the project’s website, in CORDIS and on demand.